

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

SFRP1

(secreted frizzled related protein 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

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CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic target analysis: Target Source & Hypothesis

Validated antibodies & generic knockout cell lines: YCharOS antibody characterization report

Protein constructs & expression methods: Full-length expressed in Expi293F cells

Compound Library: AD Informer Set

Biochemical assay: Time Resolved Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer (TR-FRET), GST Pull-down

Screening: SFRP1-ADAM10 PPI TR-FRET assay for HTS

Cell type specific expression: lysates and media from hiPSC derived neurons, astrocytes, and microglia

Protein expression in mouse models: 5xFAD and WT mouse brain homogenates

Biological probe discovery: characterization of immunodepletion and treatment with recombinant protein in cell models.

Knockdown studies in iPSC derived cell types

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and MDK (1,2).

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.69 (rank #1171, 95.3th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.69 out of 5 (rank #1171, 95.3th percentile). The individual score components include 1.7 of 3 for genetics, and 1.99 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of SFRP1, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. The biological domain characterization of the source module (Module 42) indicates that the proteins in this module are enriched for terms annotated to the

Structural Stabilization, Synapse, Lipid Metabolism, and APP Metabolism domains. The most significantly enriched terms from this module are “collagen-containing extracellular matrix”, “basement membrane”, and “endoplasmic reticulum lumen”. SFRP1 is annotated to GO terms from 8 biodomains, primarily to terms from the Immune Response, Apoptosis, Structural Stabilization, and Synapse biological domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer’s Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. The expression of SFRP1 is confidently detected in inhibitory neuron sub-types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Secreted frizzled-related protein 1 (SFRP1) is a secreted glycoprotein with two major functional domains—the N-terminal cysteine rich domain CRD and the C-terminal netrin-like domain (NTR). Among several identified functions, SFRP1 acts as an antagonist to the Wnt signalling pathway and inhibits the activity of metalloprotease ADAM10. Both the Wnt pathway and ADAM10 activity have been implicated as regulators of AD pathology. Further study of the role of SFRP1 and development of research tools for SFRP1 could lead to a better understanding of AD. This TEP focuses on the development of these research tools.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

SFRP1 is one of five members of the secreted glycoprotein family SFRP. As a small, dispersible extracellular ligand, SFRP1 is a multifunctional regulator of cell-cell communication. In normal development, SFRP1 has been shown to play a role in regulation of growth, differentiation, and induction of polarity of cells (3–5). Key to the protein’s multiple functions, SFRP1 contains two independent domains: the N-terminal cysteine rich domain (CRD) and the C-terminal netrin-like domain (NTR), the latter of which also binds heparin proteoglycans. SFRP1 is mainly known for acting as a Wnt antagonist by sequestering Wnt through direct binding and by binding Wnt receptor Frizzled (6). SFRP1 also binds and inhibits the activity of the metalloprotease ADAM10, for which known targets include Notch, N-Cadherin, TREM2, and APP (7–11).

SFRP1 may contribute to AD pathology through either the WNT signalling or ADAM10 secretase pathways. Downregulation of Wnt signalling promotes AD pathogenesis such as synaptic loss, A β deposition, and tau phosphorylation (4). Conversely, expression of Wnt signalling promotes neuronal survival and synaptic plasticity (4). Of further interest for AD is the interaction between SFRP1 and ADAM10. ADAM10, as the constitutive α -secretase of the brain, cleaves APP within the amyloid- β sequence (12). Thus, active ADAM10 diverts processing of APP by β - and γ -secretases and prevents the accumulation of toxic peptides, a hallmark of AD. Indeed, recent studies of SFRP1 have linked AD-related pathogenesis. SFRP1 is elevated in CSF and detergent extracts of brain samples from AD patients (13). SFRP1 null mice in an AD transgenic model system demonstrated fewer and smaller plaques, reduced gliosis, and improved performance in cognition assessments (13). In the mouse model 5xFAD, SFRP1 was found to be upregulated while ADAM10 was downregulated (14).

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

The YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for SFRP1. The YCharOS antibody characterization pipeline uses knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of available commercial antibodies for SFRP1 by immunoblot (Western blot), immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. The cell line background was chosen based on the adequate expression of the target protein.

Complete report: [SFRP1 antibody characterization report](#)

Proteins Purified

1. SFRP1-c500: Full-length Human SFRP1 (E32-E314). Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

Compound Library

At least one potent, cell active small molecule modulator of this protein is included within the AD Informer Set (<https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.07.22.453404>). Chemical tools from the AD Informer Set can be used in efforts to validate therapeutic hypotheses related to their protein targets. A physical copy of the AD Informer Set can be ordered via the TREAT-AD website: <https://treatad.org/data-tools/ad-informer-set>.

Interacting domains of SFRP1 and ADAM10

A series of VenusFlag-tagged truncation constructs of ADAM10 corresponding to known domains were generated (Fig. 1A). Constructs were co-expressed with SFRP1-GST in HEK293T cells before collection of cell lysis. Pulldown of the SFRP1-GST and probing for Flag tag of truncation constructs demonstrated that the prodomain (P) and metalloprotease domain (M) of ADAM10 bind to SFRP1 (Fig. 1B). Similarly, GST-tagged truncation constructs of SFRP1 corresponding to the Frizzled cysteine-rich domain (CRD) or the netrin domain (NTR) were generated (Fig. 2A). After co-expression with VenusFlag-tagged ADAM10 constructs as outlined in Fig. 1A in HEK293T cells, pulldown of the GST-tagged SFRP1 truncations and detection of the Flag tag of the ADAM10 truncations demonstrated that the CRD domain of SFRP1 binds ADAM10 (Fig. 2B).

Plasmids generated for these experiments are listed in Table 1 and are available through the [Addgene TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#). Materials and methods are further discussed in **Additional Information**.

Figure 1. SFRP1 binds the prodomain and disintegrin domain of ADAM10. A) Diagram of truncation constructs of ADAM10, from top to bottom: full length (FL), prodomain through cysteine-rich domain (PC), prodomain and metalloprotease domain (PM), metalloprotease through cysteine-rich domain (MC), disintegrin and cysteine-rich domain (DC), metalloprotease domain (M), and prodomain (P), B) Pulldown of SFRP1-GST tag and detection of Flag-tag from VenusFlag-tagged ADAM10 constructs as described in A when co-expressed with each other or empty VenusFlag control vector (left). Expression of constructs in whole cell lysate used for pulldown (right).

Figure 2. SFRP1 CRD domain binds ADAM10. A) Diagram of truncation constructs of SFRP1, from top to bottom: full length (FL), Frizzled cysteine-rich domain (CRD), and netrin domain (NTR), B) Pulldown of GST-tagged SFRP1 truncations as described in 3A and detection of Flag-tag from VenusFlag-tagged ADAM10 PM and PC truncations as described in 2A when co-expressed in HEK 293T cells(left). Expression of constructs in whole cell lysate used for pulldown (right).

Biochemical assay and ultra-high throughput screen assay

Time Resolved Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer (TR-FRET)

A time resolved fluorescence resonance energy transfer (TR-FRET) assay was developed for the interacting domains of ADAM10 (prodomain and metalloprotease domain (PM), Fig. 1A) and SFRP1 (cysteine-rich domain (CRD), Fig. 2A). As summarized in Fig. 3A, anti-Flag antibody labelled with terbium donor fluorophore binds N-terminal VenusFlag-tagged ADAM10-PM, and anti-GST antibody labelled with D2 acceptor

fluorophore binds N-terminal GST-tagged SFRP1-CRD. When VenusFlag-ADAM10-PM and GST-SFRP1-CRD are in proximity as occurs during protein-protein interactions (PPI), excitation of terbium results in emission of energy in range to excite D2. The emission signal of D2 therefore serves as a readout for SFRP1-CRD and ADAM10-PM PPI.

Ultra-high throughput screen (uHTS)

The TR-FRET assay for ADAM10-PM and SFRP1-CRD as described above was miniaturized and optimized in a 1536-well format for uHTS. A pilot screening of 2,036 FDA approved and bioactive compounds library was carried out to validate the uHTS TR-FRET assay for screening ADAM-10: SFRP1-CRD PPI inhibitors. The uHTS assay has shown robust performance for HTS with $S/B > 4.7$ (Fig. 3B) and $Z' > 0.6$ (Fig. 3C) across six 1536-well plates. The hit rate for the screen was 0.5% with a cutoff of % control activity less than 60 (Fig. 3D). Two primary hit compounds were confirmed with dose-response TR-FRET (Fig. 4A) and further confirmed by GST pulldown (Fig. 4B).

Plasmids generated for these experiments are listed in Table 1 and are available through [the Addgene TREAT-AD Plasmid Collection](#). Materials and methods are further discussed in **Additional Information**.

Figure 3. TR-FRET uHTS for interaction between SFRP1-CRD and ADAM10-PM. A) TR-FRET diagram for GST-SFRP1-CRD and VenusFlag-ADAM10-PM interaction (truncations as described in Fig. 1A and Fig. 2A), B) Signal to Background ratio (S/B) (B) and Z' factor (C) of SFRP1-CRD and ADAM10-PM TR-FRET pilot uHTS, D) Scatter plot summary of results from 2036 FDA approved and bioactive compounds screened by 1536-well uHTS TR-FRET

Figure 4. Validation of pilot uHTS hits. A) Dose-response TR-FRET for Compound 1 and Compound 2 in 100x diluted cell lysate co-expressing GST-SFRP1-CRD and VenusFlag-ADAM10-PM, B) Pulldown of GST-tagged SFRP1 (full length) and detection of Flag-tagged ADAM10 (full length) in the presence of 25 μ M or 100 μ M of Compound 1 or 2 or equivalent DMSO, C) Structure of Compound 1 (PubChem SID 26634819) and Compound 2 (PubChem SID 26633395).

Cell type specific expression:

Using anti-human SFRP1 antibody ab126613 as appears in the [YCharOS SFRP1 Antibody Characterization Report](#), SFRP1 expression was easily detected in human iPSC-derived neurons and astrocytes but minimally detected in human iPSC-derived microglia (Fig. 5). See **Additional Information** for cell line information, iPSC differentiation protocols, and Western blot conditions.

Figure 5. Expression of SFRP1 in whole cell lysates (top) and media (bottom) across neurons (N), astrocytes (A), and microglia (M) derived from iPSC cell lines WTC11 (left) and F033K (right). Independent samples ($n=2$) were run in adjacent lanes.

Protein expression in mouse models:

Anti-SFRP1 (Abcam ab267466) reacted with a band \sim 35 kDa in mouse brain homogenates (Fig 6A). Further, SFRP1 was expressed in the mouse brain homogenates at rate a 11.9 times greater expression in 5xFAD mice

compared to wildtype age matched C57BL/6J control mice (WT) (Fig 6B) (15).

Figure 6. SFRP1 expression in 5xFAD and WT (C57BL/6J) mouse brain homogenates. A) Western blot of crude protein extract from brain homogenates of $n=4$ 5XFAD and $n=4$ C57BL/6J B) Quantification SFRP1 expression, $***p < 0.001$.

Biological probe discovery:

- 1) **Immunodepletion of secreted protein in medium** : SFRP1 was immunoprecipitated from media conditioned with WTC11-derived neurons. SFRP1 was measured in eluate following immunoprecipitation by Western blot and unbound SFRP1 was detected in flowthrough by Western blot and ELISA (Fig. 7). See **Additional Information** for experimental information on immunoprecipitation, Western blotting, and ELISAs.

Figure 7. Immunoprecipitation (IP) of SFRP1 using validated antibody ab126613 from WTC11 iPSC-derived neuron conditioned media A) Western blot of eluted SFRP1 (bottom) and unbound SFRP1 in flowthrough (top) from media samples, $n=3$ technical replicates of single sample collection loaded in three adjacent lanes B) ELISA quantifying amount of remaining SFRP1 in flowthrough after immunoprecipitation. PBS and IgG were used for negative controls for immunoprecipitation across experiments, $*p < 0.05$ and $****p < 0.0001$, $n=3$ technical replicates.

- 2) **Cell-based assays following immunodepletion**: To understand the impact of modulating SFRP1 on cell function, we performed a small panel of assays on cells treated with anti-SFRP1 antibody. WTC11 iPSC-derived neurons were treated with anti-SFRP1 before measuring A β 40 and A β 42 in conditioned media (Fig. 8). iPSC-derived astrocytes were treated with anti-SFRP1 before measuring IL-6 in conditioned media (Fig. 9). Treatment with anti-SFRP1 very slightly increased A β 42 levels and A β 42:A β 40 in iPSC-neurons and increased IL-6 levels in iPSC-astrocytes. See **Additional Information** for experimental information.

Figure 8. Immunodepletion of SFRP1 from iPSC derived neurons by treatment with anti-SFRP1 antibody. Aβ40 and Aβ42 levels in WTC11 neuron conditioned media when treated with anti-SFRP1 antibody or IgG as measured by ELISA, n=4 independent experiments. *p<0.05 and ns= p>0.05.

Figure 9. Immunodepletion of SFRP1 from iPSC derived astrocytes by treatment with anti-SFRP1 antibody. IL-6 levels in WTC11 astrocyte conditioned media when treated with anti-SFRP1 antibody or IgG as measured by ELISA, n=2 independent experiments. *p<0.05.

- 3) **Cell-based assays following treatment with recombinant protein:** To understand the impact of modulating SFRP1 on cell function, we performed a small panel of assays on cells treated with recombinant SFRP1. WTC11 iPSC-derived astrocytes were treated with recombinant SFRP1 before measuring cell viability (Fig. 10A), cytotoxicity (Fig. 10B), and mitochondrial function (Fig. 10C). Treatment with recombinant SFRP1 protein did not have any toxic effects on the astrocytes as indicated by the alamarBlue and LDH experiments. Recombinant SFRP1 protein treatment did not have any significant effect on mitochondrial function. See **Additional Information** for experimental details.

Figure 10. Activity of WTC11 iPSC-derived astrocytes following SFRP1 protein treatment. A) AlamarBlue viability assay B) LDH cytotoxicity assay C) Mitotracker assay, n=3 independent experiments, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$. BSA serves as control.

Knockdown studies in iPSC derived cell types

shRNA targeting SFRP1 was used to knockdown SFRP1 expression in WTC11 iPSC-derived neurons. Treatment with shSFRP1 slightly increased A β 40 levels and consequently decreased A β 42:A β 40 slightly in neuron conditioned media (Fig. 11).

Figure 11. Knockdown of SFRP1 by shRNA in WTC11 iPSC derived neurons. A) Approx. 40% knockdown of SFRP1 mRNA confirmed by RT-qPCR in cell lysate B) A β 40 (left) and A β 42 (middle) levels and A β 42:A β 40 (right) in WTC11 neuron conditioned media. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, ns= $p > 0.05$

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of SFRP1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on Addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

1. SFRP1-c500: Full-length Human SFRP1 (E32-E314). Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

Construct ID	SFRP1-c500
Parental vector	pHL-avitag3
Tag	C-terminal His6, C-terminal Avitag
Protein mass (with tag and secretion signal)	39227.9 Da
Extinction Coefficient (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	40910
Protein sequence (with tag)	MGILPSPGMPALLSLVSLLSVLLMGCVAETGSEYDYVSFQSDIGPYQSGRFYTKPPQCVDIPA DLRLCHNVGYKKMVLPNLLEHETMAEVKQQASSWVPLLNKNCHAGTQVFLCSLFAPVCLD RPIYPCRWLCEAVRDSCEPVMQFFGFYWPEMLKCDKFPEGDVLCIAMTPPNATEASKPQGT TVCPPCDNELKSEAIIEHLCASEFALRMKIKEVKKENGDKKIVPKKKKPLKLGPIKKKDLKLLVL YLKNGADCPCHQLDNLSSHFLIMGRKVKSQYLLTAHKWDKKNKEFKNFMKKMKNHECPT FQSVFKGTGGSGGSLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGRTKHHHHHH

Intact Mass Deconvolution: SFRP1-c500 (with tag)	N/A
Observed Mass:	
Protein yield:	1 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>Mammalian</i> : Expi293F cells (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Expression medium	FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Plasmid purification	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain MACH1. Plate on LB-agar plates containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml). Inoculate 5 ml LB broth containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml) with a single colony and grow 6h at 37°C with shaking. Inoculate 800 ml LB broth containing the same antibiotic with 2 ml of starter culture and grow overnight at 37°C with shaking. Split culture into 4 and perform MaxiPrep (Qiagen) with 4 columns according to manufacturer's instructions. Add 0.7 volumes of isopropanol to precipitate the plasmid. Spin (17000g, 30 min, 4°C) and wash pellet with 70% ethanol. Resuspend plasmid with sterile TE buffer under sterile conditions. Yield is typically 2 mg of plasmid.
Transfection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Split Expi293F cells to 1×10^6 cells/ml in 200 ml FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium. Incubate for 24 h until cells are approximately 2×10^6 cells/ml (37°C, 150 rpm, 8% CO₂, 75% rh). 2. Add plasmid to 4mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 0.5 µg/ml final concentration. 3. Add linear PEI (1 mg/ml sterile stock) to another 4mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 3 µg/ml final concentration. 4. Add the mixture from Step 3 to the one in Step 2 and incubate at room temperature for 30 min. 5. Add the plasmid/PEI mixture slowly to the cells. 6. Add sodium butyrate (1 M sterile stock) to 12 mM final concentration. 7. Incubate cells at 30°C (8%CO₂/75% rh) with shaking at 150 rpm. 8. Harvest cell culture supernatant at 5 days post transfection (900g, 20 min, 4°C). 9. Filter supernatant through 0.2 µm filter.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ni IMAC W10 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 2. Ni IMAC W25 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 25 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 3. Ni IMAC elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 250 mM imidazole, 2% glycerol 4. Heparin W1 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 2% glycerol

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Heparin W2 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 2% glycerol 6. Heparin elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 1.5 M NaCl, 1% glycerol 7. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Ni IMAC W10 buffer. 8. Hi-Trap Heparin HP Column (Cytiva), equilibrated in Heparin W1 buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add imidazole to filtered supernatant to 10 mM final concentration. 2. Add a total of 2.5 ml equilibrated Ni-sepharose beads to the cell supernatant, split into 50-ml falcon tubes. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 3. Spin beads/supernatant slurry (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant supernatant and wash beads with 100 ml W10 buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml W10. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 4. Wash column with 25 ml W25. 5. Elute protein with 1x 10 ml elution buffer, followed by 2x5 ml elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. Pool elution fractions containing protein.
Purification step 2: Heparin affinity chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Apply EB fractions containing the protein, using a syringe 'drop to drop' onto the column. 2. Wash the column with 10 ml of W1, followed by 10 ml of W2. 3. Elute protein with 3x 2ml heparin elution buffer. 4. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using UV spectroscopy. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

Interacting domains, TR-FRET, and uHTS assays

HEK293T cell culture and transfection

HEK293T cells (ATCC, CRL-3216) were plated at 5×10^5 cells/well in 6 well plates and cultured in media (DMEM with 10% FBS and 1% penicillin-streptomycin) in 37° C and 5% CO₂ cell incubator overnight. At 24 hours with cell confluency approximately 70%, transfection was performed with a transfection mixture of 100 µL OPTIMUM, 3 µg plasmid total, and 9 µL of polyethylenimine 1mg/mL incubated at room temperature for 15 min and added to the well. Cells were incubated at 37° C for another 48 hours before harvesting for further experiments including TR-FRET and GST pulldown.

Plasmids generated for these experiments are listed in Table 1 and are available through [the Addgene TREAT-AD Plasmid Collection](#).

TABLE 1

Protein	N-terminal tag	C-terminal tag	Amino acids	Domains	Addgene #	Addgene name
SFRP1-CRD	V5	none	53-166	Frizzled cysteine-rich (CRD)	189544	pcDNA3.2-V5-DEST-hSFRP1(aa53-166)
SFRP1-CRD	GST	none	53-169	Frizzled cysteine-rich (CRD)	189545	pDEST27-GST-hSFRP1(aa53-169)
SFRP1-CRD	VenusFlag	none	53-169	Frizzled cysteine-rich (CRD)	189546	pSCM167-Venus-VF-hSFRP1(aa53-169)
SFRP1-CRD	Flag	none	53-169	Frizzled cysteine-rich (CRD)	189547	pSCM167-Flag-hSFRP1(aa53-169)
SFRP1-NTR	GST	none	181-314	Netrin (NTR)	189548	pDEST27-GST-hSFRP1(aa181-314)
SFRP1-NTR	V5	His	181-314	Netrin (NTR)	189549	pcDNA3.2-V5-DEST-hSFRP1(aa181-314)-his
SFRP1-NTR	VenusFlag	none	181-314	Netrin (NTR)	189550	pSCM167-Venus-VF-hSFRP1(aa181-314)
SFRP1-NTR	Flag	none	181-314	Netrin (NTR)	189551	pSCM167-Flag-hSFRP1(aa181-314)
ADAM10-P	VenusFlag	none	1-213	Pro	189554	pSCM167.2-Venus-VF-hADAM10(aa1-213)
ADAM10-P	V5	GST	1-213	Pro	189562	pcDNA3.2-V5-DEST-hADAM10(aa1-213)-GST
ADAM10-D	VenusFlag	none	455-550	Disintegrin	189556	pSCM167.2-Venus-VF-hADAM10(aa455-550)
ADAM10-C	VenusFlag	none	551-654	Cysteine-rich	189557	pSCM167.2-Venus-VF-hADAM10(aa551-654)
ADAM10-PC	VenusFlag	none	1-654	Pro, metalloprotease, disintegrin, and cysteine-rich	189558	pSCM167.2-Venus-VF-hADAM10(aa1-654)
ADAM10-PM	VenusFlag	none	1-459	Pro and metalloprotease	189559	pSCM167-Venus-VF-hADAM10(aa1-459)
ADAM10-MC	VenusFlag	none	220-654	Metalloprotease, disintegrin, and cysteine-rich	189560	pSCM167-Venus-VF-hADAM10(aa220-654)
ADAM10-DC	VenusFlag	none	455-654	Disintegrin and cysteine-rich	189561	pSCM167-Venus-VF-hADAM10(aa455-654)
SFRP1	Flag	none	1-314	Full length	189538	pSCM167-Flag-hSFRP1
SFRP1	His	none	1-314	Full length	189539	pDEST26-his-hSFRP1
SFRP1	V5	His	1-314	Full length	189540	pcDNA3.2-V5-DEST-hSFRP1-his
SFRP1	VenusFlag	none	1-314	Full length	189541	pSCM167.2-Venus-VF-hSFRP1
SFRP1	V5	VenusFlag	1-314	Full length	189542	pcDNA3.2-V5-DEST-hSFRP1-VF
SFRP1	V5	GST	1-314	Full length	189543	pcDNA3.2-V5-DEST-hSFRP1-GST
ADAM10	VenusFlag	none	1-748	Full length	189552	pSCM167.2-Venus-VF-hADAM10
ADAM10	GST	none	1-748	Full length	189553	pDEST27-GST-hADAM10

Cell lysate collection of HEK 293T

Cells were lifted from each well, media discarded, and pellets lysed in 200 μ L of cell lysis buffer (20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 137 mM NaCl, 2 mM EDTA, 0.5% TritonX100, 1x Sigma protease inhibitor cocktail, and 1x sigma phosphatase inhibitor cocktail 2 and 3), sonicated 10 sec, incubate 10 min on ice, and centrifuged at > 16,000 g for 10 min.

TR-FRET assay for pilot ultra-high throughput screen

GST-SFRP1-CRD and VenusFlag-ADAM10-PM were co-transfected at a 1:2 plasmid ratio in HEK293T cells. Cells were lysed with cell lysis buffer. The cell lysates were diluted 120x in FRET buffer (20mM Tris, pH 7.0, 0.01% Nonidet P40, and 50mM NaCl). Anti-GST-D2 and anti-Flag-Tb antibodies (Cisbio 61GSTDLF and 61FG2TLF) were diluted at 1:1000 in the FRET buffer. The mixture was then dispensed at 5 μ L per well into 1,536-well black plates. 0.1 μ L of library compound (1 mM) dissolved in DMSO was added using pintoole integrated with Beckman NX (Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA). The final compound concentration was 20 mM, and the final DMSO concentration was 2%. After incubating at 4 $^{\circ}$ C for 16 h, TR-FRET signals were measured using PHERAstar FSX plate reader. TR-FRET signal is calculated by ratio of the emission fluorescence of the acceptor fluorophore (D2) divided by the excitation donor fluorescence (F665nm/F620nm) and multiplying by 10,000.

Screening data were analyzed using Bioassay software from CambridgeSoft (Cambridge, MA). The S/B and Z' in uHTS format were calculated. The effect of compound on the interaction TR-FRET signal was expressed as percentage of control and calculated as the following equation:

% of control = $((\text{FRET}_{\text{sample}} - \text{FRET}_{\text{blank}}) / (\text{FRET}_{\text{control}} - \text{FRET}_{\text{blank}})) * 100\%$, where FRET_{sample} is the FRET signal from sample condition, FRET_{blank} is the FRET signal from TR-FRET antibodies only wells not containing cell lysate, which defines the lowest signal. FRET_{control} is FRET signal from lysate mixture with TR-FRET antibodies, which defines the highest signal.

GST pulldown

180 μ L of cell lysate as prepared above was rotated for 2 hours at 4 $^{\circ}$ C with 30 μ L glutathione resin slurry (50% v/v in cell lysis buffer). Samples were centrifuged at 2000 rpm x 1 min, supernatant discarded, mixed by inverting the tube 10

times, and pellet washed 3 times with 1 mL lysis buffer. After final wash, pellet was mixed by vortex with 30 μ L of gel loading buffer and then boiled for 5 min. Samples were centrifuged and stored at -20 °C. Samples were electrophoresed on 10% SDS-PAGE gels at 150V for 60 min before being transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane at 100 V at 4 °C for 2-3 hours in transfer buffer (25 mM Tris, 192 mM glycine, pH 8.3, 20% ethanol vol/vol). Membrane was blocked and probed for noted target. Antibodies used as probes are as follows: monoclonal Anti-FLAG M2-HRP antibody (A8592-1MG, Sigma, 1:2500 dilution) and anti-SFRP1 (ab126613, Abcam, 1:1 000 dilution and Cell signaling, 3534S, 1:1000 dilution).

Cell line information for iPSCs

The familial Alzheimer's disease (fAD) iPSC line (F033K) was previously generated from fibroblasts of a patient carrying the APP V717I (London) mutation (16). The well-characterized WTC11 iPSC line(17) and the F033K line were cultured in mTeSR1 medium (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 85850) on cell culture treated dishes coated with Geltrex LDEV-Free Reduced Growth Factor Basement Membrane Matrix (Gibco/Thermo Fisher Scientific; Cat. No. A1413201) diluted 1:100 in DMEM/F-12 (Gibco/Thermo Fisher Scientific; Cat. No. 11320033). Briefly, mTeSR1 was replaced every other day or every day once 50% confluent. When 80-90% confluent, cells were passaged, which entailed the following: aspirating media, washing with DPBS, incubating with ReLeSR (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0484) at RT for 3 minutes, aspirating ReLeSR, and incubating at 37°C for 10 minutes, resuspending in mTeSR1 supplemented with 10nM Y-27632 dihydrochloride ROCK inhibitor (Tocris; Cat. No. 125410), counting, and plating onto Matrigel-coated plates at desired number.

iPSC differentiation protocols

Astrocytes: Human iPSC-derived astrocytes (iAs) were generated as previously described (18). Briefly, iPSCs were plated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates and infected with rtTA, SOX9, and NFIB lentivirus. On Day 0, medium was replaced with fresh mTeSR-1 medium containing 2.5 μ g/mL doxycycline. From Day 1-7, iAs were cultured in expansion medium (DMEM/F12, 10% FBS, 1% N2, 1.25 μ g/mL puromycin, 200 μ g/mL Hygromycin) and gradually transitioned to FGF medium (Neurobasal, 2% B27, 1% NEAA, 1% GlutaMax, 1% FBS, 8 ng/mL FGF, 5 ng/mL CNTF, 10 ng/mL BMP4, 200 μ g/mL Hygromycin) by Day 7. On Day 7, iAs were dissociated using Accutase for 10 minutes, and replated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates in FGF medium. From Day 9, FGF medium was changed to Maturation medium (1:1 DMEM/F12 and Neurobasal, 1% N2, 1% Na Pyruvate, 10 μ g/ μ L NAC, 10 μ g/ μ L hbEGF, 10 ng/mL CNTF, 10 ng/mL BMP4, 500 μ g/mL cAMP) and half of the medium was changed every 2 to 3 days.

Neurons: Human iPSC-derived neurons (iNs) were generated as previously described (19). Briefly, iPSCs were plated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates and infected with rtTA and NGN2 lentivirus. On Day 0, medium was replaced with fresh mTeSR-1 medium containing 2.5 μ g/mL doxycycline. From Day 1-3, iNs were cultured in K2B medium (KO DMEM, 15% KSR, 1% NEAA, 0.1% BME, 1% GlutaMax, 2 μ g/ml doxycycline) and gradually transitioned to N2B medium (DMEM/F12, 1% GlutaMax, 1.5% dextrose, 1% N2, 2 μ g/ml doxycycline, 1 μ g/mL puromycin) by Day 3. On Day 4, iNs were dissociated using Accutase for 5 minutes, and replated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates in NBM medium (Neurobasal, 1% GlutaMax, 1.5% dextrose, 0.5% NEAA, 2% B27, 10 ng/ml BDNF, 10 ng/ml GDNF, 10 ng/ml CNTF, 2 μ g/ml doxycycline, 1 μ g/mL puromycin) and half of the medium was changed every 2 to 3 days.

Microglia: Human iPSC-derived microglia-like cells (iMGL) were generated by first differentiating human iPSCs into hematopoietic progenitor cells using the STEMdiff Hematopoietic Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 05310) per manufacturer's instructions. Then, hematopoietic progenitor cells were differentiated into microglia using the STEMdiff Microglia Differentiation Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0019) and matured using STEMdiff Microglia Maturation Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0020) following the manufacturer's instructions.

Western blotting

Media were collected and spun at 5000 X g for 10 min. The supernatants were stored at -80°C. For Western blotting, 1/3 volume of 4x Laemmli protein sample buffer (BioRad, 1610747) was added to culture media. After boiling at 98°C for 5 min. For cell lysate collection, after removing media, cells were washed with PBS twice and collected in PBS with a cell scraper. Cells were spun at 3000 rpm for 5 min, and the supernatants were discarded. Cells were lysed in NP-40 buffer (1% nonidet P-40, 20 mM Tris (PH 7.4), 137 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol) with protease inhibitor (Sigma, P8340) and phosphatase inhibitor (Sigma, P5726 and P0044). 1/3 volume of 4x Laemmli protein sample buffer (BioRad, #1610747) was added to lysate and samples were boiled at 98°C for 5 min. For Western blotting, cell culture media and lysates

were separated on 12.5% Tris-glycine SDS-polyacrylamide gels. Proteins were transferred to 0.2 µm nitrocellulose membrane (BioRad, 1620112). The membrane was blocked with 5% non-fat milk for 1 hr and incubated with SFRP1 antibody (Abcam, ab126613) with 1:1000 dilution in TBST containing 3% BSA at 4°C overnight with gentle rocking. The membrane was washed with TBST for 10 mins three times and then incubated with the secondary antibody (Jackson ImmunoResearch Laboratories, #111-035-003) at 1:5000) at room temperature for 1 hr. After washing with TBST for 10 mins three times, images were taken with the ChemiDoc Imaging System (BioRad, 12003153).

Mouse brain tissue homogenate preparation and Western blotting

Methods in full are published in Doolen et al. 2023 (15). Briefly, 9-month aged adult male and female 5xFAD (JAX MMRRC Stock #034840; B6.Cg-Tg (APPSwFlon, PSEN1^{*M146L}*L286V)6799Vas/Mmjax), which are congenic on the C57BL/6J substrain and C57BL/6J (JAX stock #000664) were used for these studies. For terminal tissue collection, the brain was extracted following decapitation, cerebellum was removed, and the cortex was bisected into left and right hemispheres then snap frozen and stored at -80 °C until use. Each hemibrain immersed in 1 ml/100 mg tissue homogenization buffer (THB; 2 mM Tris (pH 7.4), 250 mM sucrose 0.5 mM EDTA 0.5 mM EGTA) supplemented with 1X Pierce Protease Inhibitor (Thermo Scientific #A32953) and 1x Phosphatase Inhibitor Cocktail 2 (Sigma-Aldrich #P5726) and homogenized for 20 sec on ice beginning at medium and increasing to high speed. Total protein concentration of the resulting homogenate was measured using a Bradford assay by comparing samples to a standard curve known concentrations of Albumin Standard.

Western blots were reproduced and confirmed from initial pilot data, under blinded conditions. 25 µg of protein from N=4 individual 5xFAD subjects and homogenate from N=4 individual C57BL/6J subjects, were prepared in 1x loading buffer (4x: 4 ml 100% glycerol, 2.4 ml 1M Tris/HCl (pH 6.8), 0.8 g SDS, 4 mg bromophenol blue, 3.1 ml H₂O, 0.5 ml beta-mercaptoethanol) and incubated at 95 °C for 5 min. Samples were separated with SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (4–15% Mini-PROTEAN TGX™ Precast Protein Gels, 10-well, 30 µl, Bio-rad #4561083) using 120 V for 60 min, then transferred onto a nitrocellulose membrane using at 25 V for 30 min. Following blocking of non-specific using EveryBlot Blocking Buffer (Bio-rad #12010020) for 5 min at room temperature with gentle rocking, blots were immersed in anti-SFRP1 primary antibody (Abcam ab267466) diluted 1:1000 in EveryBlot Blocking Buffer overnight at 4 °C with gentle rocking and then in 1:1000 fluorescent secondary antibody (StarBright blue 700 goat anti-rabbit IgG, Bio-rad #12004161) and 1:2000 hFAB™ Rhodamine Anti-GAPDH Antibody (Bio-rad #12004167) for 1 h at room temperature. Membranes were scanned with a Bio-rad ChemiDoc MP Imaging System, and pixel intensity was quantified using ImageJ with statistical analyses and graphing performed using GraphPad Prism Version 9.3.1.

ELISA

SFRP1 level in culture media was measured by ELISA (Abcam, ab277082). ELISA was performed following the instruction of the manufacturer. To make the measurement accurate, the media were diluted 5-50 folds based on the optimization.

Immunoprecipitation

Cell culture media were collected as described above for Western blotting. SFRP1 antibody (Abcam, ab126613) was added to media (0.75 µg/ml) and incubated at 4°C overnight with gentle rocking. Protein A/G beads (Santa Cruz, sc-2003) were prewashed with PBS twice and resuspended with lysis buffer after final wash. 30 µl slurry of resuspended beads were added to media which were incubated with the antibody. After two hours incubation at 4°C, beads were pelleted by centrifugation at 3,000 rpm (approximately 1,000xg) for 30 seconds at 4°C. The supernatants were collected to serve as flowthrough. Beads were washed with PBS 3 times. 30-50 ul 2x Laemmli sample buffer (BioRad, 1610737) was added to the beads pellet. After boiling for 5 minutes, samples can be stored at -20°C for Western blotting.

Immunodepletion in cell media

SFRP1 antibody (Abcam, ab126613) was added to media (0.75 µg/ml) with iPSC derived cells. The cells were further cultured for 3 days at 37°C in humidified conditions with 5% CO₂. Cell culture media were collected as described above for Western blotting. Prewashed protein A/G beads were added to media and incubated at 4°C for two hours. The following steps are the same as immunoprecipitation for cell media described above.

Protein treatment of cells

iPSc-derived astrocytes were cultured on 96-well plates. Cells were treated with SFRP1 protein (purified in house, see methods above) in 100 µl media on day 14 for 24 hours.

Measurement of A β and IL-6

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits specific for human A β 40 and A β 42 (Invitrogen: #KHB3482 and #KHB3441) and IL-6 (R&D Systems: #QK206) were used to quantify A β species and IL-6 according to the manufacturer's instructions. Results were expressed as percentages of the isotype control. The means from duplicate measurements are presented.

AlamarBlue viability assay

20 μ l CellTiter-Blue reagent (Promega, #G8088) was added to each well of a 96-well plate. After incubating for 4 hours at 37°C, Fluorescence Intensity (FI), which corresponds to the number of living cells, was measured with PHERAstar FSX (BMG Labtech) plate reader (Ex. 560nm and Em. 590nm). Wells containing medium only were used to determine background signal.

LDH cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity assay was performed using kit (Promega, J2380). Cell culture medium was diluted 20 fold with LDH storage buffer (200mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.3), 10% Glycerol, 1% BSA). 50 μ l diluted culture medium was mixed with 50 μ l LDH detection reagent in a 96-well opaque-walled, non-transparent assay plate with opaque bottom. After 60 minutes incubation at room temperature, luminescence signal was measured with EnVision 2103 Multilabel plate Reader (PerkinElmer).

Mitotracker assay

To stain mitochondria, mitochondrial membrane potential indicator, TMRM (ThermoFisher, #134361), was diluted in culture medium containing the nuclear indicator Hoechst 33342. 5 μ l staining solution was added to each well to final concentration of 100 nM TMRM and 10 μ g/ml Hoechst 33342. After 30 minutes incubation at 37°C, cells were imaged with ImageXpress[®] Micro (Molecular Devices), and the fluorescence intensity of the cells was quantified with MetaXpress 6. Carbonyl cyanide-p-trifluoromethoxyphenylhydrazone (FCCP) was used as positive control at 100 μ M. 30 minutes before adding staining solution, FCCP was added to cells at final concentration of 100 μ M.

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